

Faculty of Applied and Creative Arts

**Visitor Attention Span and Museum Learning:
The Influence of Exhibit Type and Interactivity**

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Visitor Attention Span and Museum Learning:
The Influence of Exhibit Type and Interactivity

NG YEN YEN

This project is submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of exhibit type on visitor attention span and engagement at the Borneo Cultures Museum, within the broader context of declining global attention spans. While existing literature indicates that average attention has reduced to approximately 8 seconds in recent years, limited research has examined how this trend affects museum experiences in Malaysia. Using observational methods, this study compared visitor engagement between a static informational exhibit (Kelidieng Burial Pole) and an interactive visual exhibit (Puteri Santubong). The findings reveal that the interactive exhibit elicited significantly longer attention (143 seconds on average) and greater engagement than the static exhibit (28 seconds). These results suggest that interactive elements can effectively counteract reduced attention spans and enhance visitor experience. This research contributes to the broader field of museum studies by offering localized insights and emphasizes the need for Malaysian museums to adopt interactive strategies to maintain visitor interest and support informal learning outcomes.

Keywords: Museum engagement, Visitor attention span, Interactive exhibits, Static exhibits, Informal learning, Malaysian museum studies.

ABSTRAK

Kajian ini menyelidik kesan jenis pameran terhadap tempoh perhatian dan penglibatan pengunjung di Muzium Kebudayaan Borneo, dalam konteks global yang lebih luas mengenai pengurangan tempoh perhatian. Walaupun literatur sedia ada menunjukkan bahawa perhatian purata telah berkurang kepada kira-kira 8 saat dalam beberapa tahun kebelakangan ini, kajian mengenai bagaimana trend ini memberi kesan terhadap pengalaman muzium di Malaysia adalah terhad. Dengan menggunakan kaedah pemerhatian, kajian ini membandingkan penglibatan pengunjung antara pameran maklumat statik (Tiang Penguburan Kelidieng) dan pameran visual interaktif (Puteri Santubong). Hasil kajian menunjukkan bahawa pameran interaktif menarik perhatian yang lebih lama (143 saat secara purata) dan penglibatan yang lebih tinggi berbanding dengan pameran statik (28 saat). Keputusan ini mencadangkan bahawa elemen interaktif dapat berkesan dalam menangani pengurangan tempoh perhatian dan meningkatkan pengalaman pengunjung. Kajian ini memberi sumbangan kepada bidang kajian muzium secara lebih luas dengan menawarkan pandangan yang disesuaikan dengan konteks tempatan dan menekankan keperluan muzium di Malaysia untuk mengamalkan strategi interaktif bagi mengekalkan minat pengunjung dan menyokong hasil pembelajaran tidak formal.

Kata kunci: *Penglibatan muzium, Julat perhatian pelawat, Pameran interaktif, Pameran statik, Pembelajaran tidak formal, Kajian muzium di Malaysia*

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the researcher introduces the background and context of the study, discusses the research problem, questions, and objectives, and outlines the significance and scope of the research. This chapter sets the stage for understanding the impact of museum exhibit designs, particularly digital and interactive elements, on visitor attention spans in Malaysia. Additionally, it identifies the gaps in existing literature and explains the significance of the study in contributing to the field of museum research.

1.2 Research Background

Museums are key cultural institutions for public education, heritage preservation, and engaging with history and art. Over the past few decades, museum exhibits have been increasingly enhanced with digital and interactive elements to improve the visitor experience. However, how these elements affect visitor attention spans, and how this varies across cultures and technologies, remains underexplored.

Most studies on visitor attention spans, such as Serrell's influential works, '*Are They Watching?* (2002)' and '*Paying Attention: Duration and Allocation of Visitors' Time in Museum Exhibitions* (1997)', have been conducted in the United States. While these studies are foundational, they are over a decade old and focused on Western audiences interacting with less technologically advanced exhibits. As such, their findings may not apply to today's museums, especially in Malaysia, where cultural and technological contexts have evolved. Additionally, the untested claim that human attention spans are shorter than a goldfish's (8 seconds) has yet to be proven in the museum setting.

A clear gap exists in research on the attention spans of museum visitors in Malaysia. With the increasing integration of digital technology and interactive displays in local museums, it is crucial to explore how these elements influence visitor

engagement and whether Western research findings are applicable to Malaysian audiences. Moreover, the impact of different content types (digital, interactive, traditional) on attention span has not been examined.

This study aims to fill these gaps by investigating the average attention span of visitors in Malaysian museums, focusing on how exhibit designs particularly those with interactive or digital elements affect the time spent engaging with exhibits. By focusing on Malaysian museums which is the Borneo Cultures Museum, this research will provide more localized insights into the factors that contribute to a successful, engaging museum experience.

1.2.1 Definition of terms

1. Attention Span

The duration in which you can remain engaged or pay close attention to something.

2. Museum Exhibit

A display of items presented to the public in a museum.

3. Engagement

The state of being engaged or participating in something.

1.2.2 History

In museums, history is kept alive, people are curious, and information is shared. "Museum" comes from the Latin word for "temple," which shows that they were first used as holy places to honour the Muses, who were goddesses of creativity. In the past, places like the Library of Alexandria were places where people could learn. Rich people in the Renaissance put art and natural wonders on show in "cabinets of curiosities." In the 18th century, these turned into public museums like the British Museum and the Louvre.

In Malaysia, museums hold a special role in celebrating and protecting the country's diverse heritage. The National Museum (Muzium Negara), opened in 1963, showcases Malaysia's history from prehistoric times to independence in a striking Minangkabau-style building. State museums like the Sarawak Museum and the Penang State Museum highlight local cultures, traditions, and histories.

These days, Malaysian museums are coming up with creative ways to keep visitors interested. The Islamic Arts Museum Malaysia brings Islamic history to life through interactive displays and stories. The Melaka Maritime Museum, on the other hand, lets people learn about history on a model Portuguese ship. But, like most museums around the world, it can be hard to keep people's attention on exhibits where most people only look at them for 15 to 30 seconds.

To get around this, museums are using technology. Tech-savvy tourists are drawn to virtual tours, augmented reality, and multimedia displays. Families and school groups are drawn to hands-on activities like craft demonstrations and interactive zones. Visitors can take in what they've seen at their own pace in quiet places where they can think.

Malaysian museums are a testament to the balance between preserving history and staying relevant in a fast-changing world. Through their innovative efforts, they connect the past and present, creating meaningful experiences for generations to come.

1.3 Problem Statement

The evolution of technology and the proliferation of digital content have significantly impacted attention spans. Studies, such as Serrell (2002), indicate a decline in the average attention span of museum visitors. Furthermore, scholar claims that the average human attention span is just 8 seconds, shorter than that of a goldfish.

This decreasing attention span presents challenges not only in education but also in broader social contexts. For example, excessive screen time among toddlers has been linked to issues like speech delays.

In the context of museums as informal learning institutions, maintaining visitor attention is critical for effective information absorption. However, traditional static exhibits increasingly struggle to engage audiences accustomed to dynamic, fast-paced digital media.

Thus, this research aims to investigate the average attention span of museum visitors, focusing on how exhibit types (digital, interactive, or traditional) influence engagement and how museums can adapt to meet the needs of modern audiences.

1.4 Research Question

1. What is the average attention span of visitors when engaging with different museum exhibits?
2. How do interactive and digital elements in museum exhibits affect the attention span of visitors?
3. What types of content are most effective in capturing and maintaining the attention of museum visitors?

1.5 Research Objective

1. To identify the average attention span of visitors when visiting museum exhibits.
2. To analyse how interactive and digital elements in exhibits impact the attention span of visitors.
3. To document the types of content that are most effective in capturing the visitors' attention in a museum display.

1.6 Significance of Study

This study is important because it brings insight into how the design of museum exhibits may engage visitors by focusing on the length of museum visitor's attention span. By understanding what the average attention span is and what factors work to increase or decrease attention span, museums can better create more impactful exhibits. This research will benefit Malaysian museum curators and exhibit designers who wish to enhance visitor experience through development of exhibits that will catch and hold visitors' attention. In addition, this research will help the field of museum studies with a framework that measures the efficacy of diverse kinds of content in exhibit content. This study will assist in designing future exhibit content and systems as well as educational strategies by documenting which types of content best engage visitors. Also, it will establish the groundwork for subsequent research in the role of technology for improving museum experiences and visitors' memory.

1.7 Research Scope

- i. Attention Span
- ii. Museum Exhibits
- iii. Visitor Engagement

Table 1.0*Table of Research Problem, Research Question and Research Objective*

Research Problem	Research Question	Research Objective
There is a gap in research on the attention span of visitors in Malaysian museums, especially regarding digital and interactive elements.	What is the average attention span of visitors when engaging with different museum exhibits?	To identify the average attention span of visitors when visiting museum exhibits.
The existing studies on visitor attention span are outdated and not applicable to modern museums or Malaysian contexts.	How do interactive and digital elements in museum exhibits affect the attention span of visitors?	To analyse how interactive and digital elements in exhibits impact the attention span of visitors.
There is no validated research on whether the claim that human attention spans are shorter than that of a goldfish (8 seconds) is true in a museum setting.	What types of content are most effective in capturing and maintaining the attention of museum visitors?	To document the types of content that are most effective in capturing the visitors' attention in a museum display.

Note: Table above shows the research problems, research questions and research objectives of the research.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter reviews existing literature on attention span and learning in museum settings. The review focuses on how various factors such as age, technology, and exhibit design affect visitor engagement and the retention of attention in museums. By examining previous studies, this review identifies key findings and gaps in the research, providing a foundation for the current study. The aim is to explore how visitor attention spans are measured, maintained, and lost within museum environments, and to uncover strategies for enhancing the effectiveness of museum experiences and visitor engagement.

2.2 Generational Age Ranges and Definitions

As this research investigates how attention span varies across different age groups in museums, it is crucial to define the generational categories and their corresponding age ranges. These generational groups often exhibit distinct learning behaviours, cognitive patterns, and attention capacities, which can significantly influence their engagement with museum exhibits. Understanding these differences is key to designing exhibits that cater to the needs and preferences of diverse age groups.

Figure 2.2.1

Generations Timeline

Generations timeline

Note: This figure shows the generation timeline. Retrieved from <https://www.leadershipsuccess.co/blog/the-generation-gap-myth>

The generational timeline, as illustrated by the Pew Research Center, provides a comprehensive visual representation of birth years and their corresponding generational categories spanning from 1920 to 2020. The generational cohorts identified include the silent generation (born 1928-1945), baby boomers (born 1946-1964), Generation X (born 1965-1980), Millennials (born 1981-1996), and Generation Z (born 1997 onward). This segmentation highlights the historical and sociocultural contexts that shaped the formative experiences and collective identities of each cohort.

2.2.1 Generational Cohorts and Definitions

The generational timeline below, based on the Pew Research Center's classifications, illustrates the birth years of each cohort, from the Silent Generation to Generation Z. These groups are often distinguished by unique historical, cultural, and technological experiences, which may influence their attention span and learning preferences.

- Silent Generation (born 1928-1945)
- Baby Boomers (born 1946-1964)
- Generation X (born 1965-1980)
- Millennials (born 1981-1996)
- Generation Z (born 1997-present)

Each generational cohort has different experiences with technology, media consumption, and social structures, which can shape their cognitive abilities and attention spans. Research indicates that younger generations, particularly Millennials and Generation Z, are often accustomed to fast-paced digital environments, which may shorten their attention spans in traditional museum settings. In contrast, older generations, such as Baby Boomers and the Silent Generation, may have different interaction preferences and potentially longer attention spans when engaging with more immersive or tactile exhibits.

2.2.2 The Impact of Generational Differences on Attention Span in Museums

While the generational timeline provides a useful framework, the relationship between generational identity and attention span in museums is still a developing area of study. Past research has shown that younger visitors, such as Millennials and Generation Z, often prefer interactive, tech-enhanced exhibits and are more likely to disengage in traditional, text-heavy museum displays. In contrast, older generations, like Baby Boomers, may engage more deeply with narrative-driven or object-based displays, though they may be less familiar with or attracted to high-tech, digital interactions.

This highlights the need for museums to consider these generational differences when designing exhibits that aim to capture and retain attention. For example, integrating multimedia components, gamification, and interactive technologies may be more effective for younger audiences, while providing more traditional, reflective experiences might resonate better with older visitors.

2.3 Comparative Attention Spans

As museum is said to be an informal education institute, and acts as a knowledge lab, attention span is crucial for the learning process.

According to Simon et al. (2023), attention span refers to the ability to stay focused and attentive while carrying out a routine task. To support this, Santos-Longhurst (2019) in ‘What Are the Causes of a Short Attention Span, and How Can I Improve It?’ reviewed by Dr Timothy states that poor focus during learning process leads to forgetting crucial information or details and inability to communicate efficiently.

Unfortunately, as the younger generation nowadays have been relying on gadgets and trends filled digital platforms, researchers have found out that the global attention span have been reducing (McClinton, 2021).

Figure 2.3.1

Comparison of Attention Span in Visual

Note: The comparison of attention span. Retrieved from <https://www.bridgcareaba.com/blog/average-human-attention-span>)

Based on figure 2.3.1 , it shows that in 2000, the average attention span of a human is 12 seconds, while 8 seconds in 2023 (Hollander, 2023). To validate this, a study in 2015 paid by Microsoft and written about in Time magazine showed that people can only pay attention for 8 seconds on average (Bradbury, 2016). However, in

Dr. Subramanian's 'Myth and Mystery of Shrinking Attention Span' research journal, he stated that these statements are not proven by any research.

Figure 2.3.2

The Line Chart of Average Attention Span

Note: The line graph above shows the declining of attention span.

According to the American Psychological Association (APA)'s podcast discussion on 'Why Our Attention Spans Are Shrinking' with Dr Gloria Mark, the average attention span of an individual back in 2004 on any screen is 2.5 minutes, then went down to 75 seconds in 2012. In 2024, the average attention dropped to just 8.25 seconds (*Average Human Attention Span Statistics & Facts, 2024*).

2.4 History of Museum

Before we dwell more on the attention span in museum, in museum, we first must know the history of museum, The word "museum" comes from the Ancient Greek word "mouseion," which meant "seat of the Muses" (Lewis, 2024). A "mouseion" was a place for philosophy or quiet reflection. As an institution, a museum gathers, cares for, and interprets artifacts, objects, and other natural and human history-related materials that the public can see (*History of Museums - From Oldest to Modern Museums, n.d.*).

On the other hand, in the research journal of ‘Cultural communication in museums’ by Li (2024), the perspective of visitors on museum is that museums collect, preserve, study, share and exhibits tangible and intangible objects. In the modern days, museum serves as other functions too. For example, Yi & Jamarul (2023) stated that museum has been a place where heals mental health in their ‘The Significance of The Art Museum Space As Emotional Healing’ study. Besides that, to attract new diverse groups, some museums have transformed their space into a place for social gathering (Barwick, 2020). Other than that, museums also create a platform where individuals can share their thoughts and ideas, helping to expand viewpoints and encourage greater involvement and inclusivity (Wollentz & Kuhlefeldt 2021).

2.5 Function of curator in museum

According to THE HISTORY MUSEUM CURATOR of the 21st Century by Franco (1996), curators are required to take care of the items in the museum collection such as complex information resources, curators need to go beyond their traditional duties of collection care, study, as well as interpretation.

However, in the context of curatorial, museum is a place where curators try to make sure that visitors have interesting, and educational experiences that are open to everyone (Artlyst, 2023).

2.6 Learning in Museum

As museum is said to be an informal education institute, and acts as a knowledge lab, attention span is crucial for the learning process. To support this, Santos-Longhurst (2019) in a medical blog reviewed by Dr Timothy stated that poor focus during learning process leads to forgetting crucial information or details and inability to communicate efficiently.

Table 2.6.1

Table of Average Time Spent in an Exhibit

	1997	2002	2024
Serrell (2002)	< 20 min	2.5 min	-
Castellotti et al., (2024)	-	-	46.2 sec

Note: Table above shows the average time spent of visitors in an exhibit.

Based on the Table 2.6.1, it shows that the average time spent in a exhibit is decreasing. According to the older research of 'Paying Attention: The Duration and Allocation of Visitors' Time in Museum Exhibitions' by (Serrell, 1997) studied that in average, visitors only spend less than 20 minutes in an exhibition. 5 years later in 2002, Serrell's newer research, 'Are They Watching? Visitors and Videos in Exhibitions' which experimented with 45 different videos, have found that the average time spent watching are under 3 minutes. What's worse is almost 33 out of 45 videos only watched by visitors in average of 2.5 minutes (Serrell, 2002).

Table 2.6.2

Average Time Spent in an Exhibit

	Single	Couples	Group	Family
Castellotti et al., (2024)	46.2 sec	53.4 sec	73.4 sec	40.7 sec

Note: Table 2.6.2 shows the average time spent of visitors in an exhibit according to (Castellotti et al., 2024).

To be more specific, there are obvious difference time spent between singles, couples, group and family. Based on table 2.6.2, singles average spent 46.2 seconds, couples 53.4 seconds, group 73.4 seconds and family 40.7 seconds in museum (Castellotti et al., 2024).

2.7 Leveraging Technology to Entertain Visitors in Museums

Due to how quickly information technology is changing, the process of digitising museums has become a worldwide trend that can't be stopped (Xia et al., 2024). Museums need to leverage their traditional exhibit display by incorporating electronic gadgets to attract visitors (Castellotti et al., 2024).

For example, virtual reality (VR), with virtual exhibition and augmented reality (AR) technologies (Yap et al., 2024). According to Varisha (2023) in 'Museum Virtual Tour to Retain the Popularity as the Pandemic Slows Down', virtual tours or exhibitions will remain relevant to Generation Z and Y as both of this generation have been getting along with technology. Younger people are more interested in interactive materials such as VR.

2.8 Research Gap

The research of visitor's average attention span such as Serrell's '*Are They Watching? Visitors and Videos in Exhibitions (2002)*' and '*Paying Attention: The Duration and Allocation of Visitors' Time in Museum Exhibitions (1997)*' are based on the visitors and museums in United States. Other than that, the research is taken place more than a decade ago. Back then, there are fewer high technologies integrated in the museum display or exhibits. Thus, the findings from the research are not applicable and not relevant to the museum visitors in Malaysia.

Besides that, there are no validate studies that proves the average human attention span are lesser than a goldfish which is just 8 seconds.

Thus, it would be hard and unfair to make a conclusion based on research that are not based in Malaysia. Therefore, in this research, the researcher will dwell more into identifying the average attention span of visitors in Malaysia's museum.

Table 2.8.1

Systematic Literature Review Table

References/ APA Style	Research Problem/ Research Objective/ Hypothesis (If Any)	Methodology (Sampling/ Data Collection Method/ Data Analysis Method)	Finding/ Recommendation (Rephrasing their finding statement)
<p>(Serrell, 1997)</p> <p>Serrell, B. (2002). Are They Watching? Visitors and Videos in Exhibitions. <i>Curator: The Museum Journal</i>, 45(1), 50–64. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2151-6952.2002.tb00049.x</p>	<p>Research Problem: The study investigates how the amount of time and number of stops visitors make in exhibitions can serve as indicators of learning, focusing on patterns of visitor behaviour and systematic measurements in museum exhibitions.</p> <p>Research Objective: The objective is to develop practical, cost-effective measurement systems and create a comparative database to identify "thoroughly used"</p>	<p>Sample (Who/ How much/ Sampling Method): -Adult visitors in various museums, excluding those in tour groups. -Data from 108 exhibitions across 5 museum types (science, natural history, history, art, zoos/aquariums). -Opportunistic, using self-selected participants during summative evaluations.</p> <p>Data Collection Method: -Total time visitors spent.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • studies indicate that visitors, on average, spend under 25 minutes at an exhibition • viewing times for a single artwork typically does not exceed 30s

	<p>exhibitions while enhancing museum practices for engaging diverse visitor populations.</p> <p>Hypothesis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Time spent and stops made can indicate engagement and learning. -Patterns in visitor behaviour can provide actionable insights for exhibition improvement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Number of stops made at individual exhibition elements. -Observations were gathered using standardized protocols and verified through pilot testing. <p>Data Analysis Method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Average and frequency distribution of total time and stops made. -Calculation of two indexes which is % Diligent Visitors (%DV): Percentage of visitors stopping at more than half the elements and Sweep Rate Index (SRI): Square feet per minute, to measure time spent relative to the exhibition size. -Visualization through scattergrams and statistical summaries. 	
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<p>(Serrell, 2020)</p> <p>Serrell, B. (2020). The aggregation of tracking-and-timing visitor-use data of museum exhibitions for benchmarks of “thorough use”. <i>Visitor Studies</i>, 23(1), 1-17.</p>	<p>Research Problem: The study seeks to understand how visitors engage with videos in museum exhibitions, specifically evaluating their ability to attract and hold attention and their effectiveness as educational tools in the context of competing exhibit elements.</p> <p>Research Objective: The objective is to develop practical, cost-effective measurement systems and create a comparative database to identify "thoroughly used" exhibitions while enhancing museum practices for engaging diverse visitor populations.</p>	<p>Sample (Who/ How much/ Sampling Method):</p> <p>Data Collection Method: - Tracking and Timing Studies - Questionnaires and Interviews</p> <p>Data Analysis Method - Quantitative Measures - Comparative Analysis - Qualitative Insights</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attraction power averaged 32%, with a range from 4% to 68%. • Holding power averaged 0.39, meaning visitors watched roughly 39% of each video on average. • Videos with shorter durations, strong human-interest stories, and good placement were more successful. • Seating and a clear introduction (e.g., video length and topic) improved attraction and holding power.
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<p>(Gao & Yu, 2024)</p> <p>Gao, B., & Yu, S. (2024). Upgrading museum experience: Insights into offline visitor perceptions through social media trends. <i>Emerging Trends in Drugs, Addictions, and Health</i>, 4, 100137.</p>	<p>Research Problem: The study aims to understand the offline visitor perceptions of museums using trends observed from online reviews, specifically exploring how online feedback and social media interactions can help improve museum services and visitor experiences in Jiangxi Province.</p> <p>Research Objective: To analyse visitor experiences and perceptions based on online reviews, identify correlations between online behaviours and offline experiences, and provide actionable insights for enhancing museum services and exhibitions.</p> <p>Hypothesis: Online reviews and social</p>	<p>Sample (Who/ How much/ Sampling Method): -1220 valid online reviews about the Jiangxi Provincial Museum collected from platforms such as Dianping and Ctrip between April 2020 to May 2023 -Data were gathered using web crawling tools and underwent careful screening for relevance and accuracy.</p> <p>Data Collection Method: -Online reviews were collected through web scraping from specified platforms, capturing user IDs, ratings, review content, and timestamps.</p> <p>Data Analysis Method; -Data were processed using the ROSTCM6.0 software for text</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The research highlighted visitor expectations, including a desire for more interactive, engaging, and informative exhibits. Negative reviews often pointed to areas where the museum could improve, such as making exhibits more immersive, improving navigation and signage, and enhancing customer service interactions. <p>The findings suggest that museums should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance exhibit content and provide more diverse and engaging displays. • Improve service quality, particularly in staff training and visitor interaction.
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	media trends provide a reflective measure of visitors' offline experiences and can serve as valuable inputs to optimize museum services and visitor satisfaction.	segmentation and analysed through word frequency statistics, high-frequency keyword analysis, semantic network analysis, and sentiment analysis to gain deep insights into visitor perceptions and feedback.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilize social media feedback to continuously adapt and improve their offerings. • Focus on creating a seamless and enriching visitor experience that resonates both online and offline.
(Voorde, 2023) Voorde, B. M. (2023). <i>Exploring Engagement in Science Museums: A Comparative Study of Static and Interactive Exhibitions</i> (Bachelor's thesis, University of Twente).	<p>Research Problem: The study looks at whether children engage differently in static (non-interactive) versus interactive museum displays, aiming to understand how different types of exhibits affect children's interest, behaviour, and learning.</p> <p>Research Objective: To find out how static and interactive museum exhibits affect children's learning, actions, and</p>	<p>Sample (Who/ How much/ Sampling Method): - 17 Dutch children, aged 6-12 years. - 17 participants (41.2% female and 58.8% male). - purposively selected participants selected based on their age and willingness to participate</p> <p>Data Collection Method: -observations -semi-structured interviews</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning (Cognitive Engagement): Children learned more from the interactive exhibits because they could touch and explore things themselves. • Behaviour (Behavioural Engagement): Kids spent more time and interacted more in the interactive exhibit, and they talked more

	<p>feelings so that museums can make their exhibits more engaging.</p> <p>Hypothesis:</p> <p>Interactive exhibits will make children more engaged (thinking, doing, and feeling) compared to static displays because they are more hands-on and engaging.</p>	<p>-Observations captured the children's behaviours during their visits to the exhibits</p> <p>-interviews explored their thoughts, feelings, and experiences in greater depth.</p> <p>Data Analysis Method</p> <p>-The data was analysed using a combination of coding for patterns and themes from the interviews (using software called Atlas.ti) and statistical tests, like chi-square tests, to compare engagement levels between static and interactive exhibits.</p> <p>-Observational data on behaviour was also quantified and analysed.</p>	<p>with others while exploring.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feelings (Affective Engagement): Children enjoyed the interactive exhibit more, showing more excitement and interest, while the static exhibit got fewer positive reactions.
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<p>(Castellotti et al., 2024)</p> <p>Castellotti, S., D'Agostino, O., & del Viva, M. M. (2024). Effectiveness of labels in digital art experience: psychophysiological and behavioral evidence. <i>Frontiers in Psychology</i>, 15. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1342667</p>	<p>Research Problem: The study investigates the impact of descriptive versus essential labels on the aesthetic experience of contemporary abstract paintings in a digital environment, aiming to assess whether additional information enhances the understanding, emotional response, and appreciation of art.</p> <p>Research Objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The role of descriptive labels in improving the comprehension, emotional experience, and engagement with artworks. - The differences in aesthetic experiences between digital reproductions and real museum settings. - The psychophysiological and behavioural responses to artworks with different 	<p>Sample (Who/ How much/ Sampling Method):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 60 university students (Caucasian, average age 23.1 years) with school-level art history knowledge. - 40 participants in the experimental condition, 20 in the control condition. - Non-probabilistic, based on volunteers who were art-naïve, with normal/corrected-to-normal vision and no cognitive disorders. <p>Data Collection Method:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Observation; Viewing times of paintings and reading times of labels - Eye tracking for gaze behaviour - Pupil dilation for arousal and emotional responses - Electrodermal activity (EDA) and heart rate (HR) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Descriptive labels improved comprehension, reduced perceived complexity, and evoked more positive emotions but did not increase liking or overall aesthetic appreciation. • Viewing times were similar across label types but longer descriptive labels correlated with slightly increased attention to artworks. • Participants spent less time viewing digital reproductions than real artworks but provided similar subjective evaluations. • Digital settings may normalize aesthetic experiences due to
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	<p>levels of informational support.</p> <p>Hypothesis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Descriptive labels will enhance the understanding and emotional engagement with artworks compared to essential labels. - The digital setting may produce similar subjective evaluations as a museum environment but with reduced engagement and physiological responses. 	<p>for physiological engagement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Questionnaire; Questionnaires assessing complexity, comprehension, emotions, and aesthetic evaluation. <p>Data Analysis Method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generalized Additive Mixed Models (GAMM) - two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) 	<p>increased familiarity with digital media, especially among younger, digital-native participants.</p>
<p>(Carbon, 2017)</p> <p>Carbon, C. C. (2017). Art perception in the museum: How we spend time and space in art exhibitions. <i>I-Perception</i>, 8(1). https://doi.org/10.1177/2041669517694184</p>	<p>Research Problem:</p> <p>The study explores how museum visitors engage with artworks in terms of viewing time and distance, specifically focusing on the ecological validity of art perception in a museum context compared to controlled laboratory settings.</p> <p>Research Objective:</p>	<p>Sample (Who/ How much/ Sampling Method):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 225 museum visitors (126 female; average age 43.3 years) attending a temporary exhibition featuring Gerhard Richter's paintings. - Observational, with participants unaware they were being studied (naturalistic observation). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visitors spent an average of 33.9 seconds per artwork during initial viewings, increasing to 50.5 seconds when return visits were included. • Longer viewing times were linked to smaller exhibitions with fewer artworks,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Observing museum visitors' behaviours in a real exhibition setting. - Analysing viewing times, distances, and patterns of re-engagement with artworks. - Identifying factors influencing deeper and more sustained art engagement. 	<p>Data Collection Method:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Observation; Recorded initial viewing times, viewing distances, and return visits to specific artworks using a custom Android app. - Demographic data (e.g., gender, estimated age) were also noted. <p>Data Analysis Method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Linear Regression: Used to analyse the relationship between artwork size (canvas area) and viewing distance, showing a strong correlation. - Descriptive Statistics: Employed to calculate means, medians, and probabilities for viewing times and revisit behaviours. - Comparative Analysis: Used to compare findings with prior studies to 	<p>enabling deeper engagement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Over half (55.3%) of visitors returned to at least one artwork, often spending more time on subsequent viewings. • Groups and pairs tended to spend more time discussing and viewing artworks compared to single visitors, while families had shorter viewing durations due to distractions from children. • Temporary exhibitions with limited artworks allow visitors to focus more deeply, leading to richer aesthetic experiences. • Encouraging multiple viewings and
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		validate results and assess differences.	providing space for optimal viewing distances can enhance engagement.
(Brida et al., 2014) Brida, J., Meleddu, M., Pulina, M., & Statzu, V. (2014). Time allocation in a museum: an empirical investigation. In <i>European Journal of Tourism Research</i> (Vol. 7).	<p>Research Problem: The study investigates the determinants influencing the time visitors spend at cultural sites, specifically focusing on the South Tyrol Museum of Archaeology (Ötzi Museum) in Bolzano, Italy.</p> <p>Research Objective: To analyse and identify the factors (e.g., demographics, socioeconomic characteristics, group behaviour, weather) that influence the length of time visitors allocate to the museum, using a microeconomic framework</p>	<p>Sample (Who/ How much/ Sampling Method): - Visitors to the South Tyrol Museum of Archaeology. - 724 visitors surveyed from June to August 2010. - Quota random sampling, ensuring representation by age and gender.</p> <p>Data Collection Method: Surveys: A structured questionnaire with 36 questions divided into four sections: trip information, perceptions of Bolzano as a destination, museum visit details, and socioeconomic characteristics.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visitors spent an average of 111.5 minutes at the museum, with a range of 30 minutes to 4.5 hours. • This was significantly higher than the typical 20 minutes reported in other museum studies. • Males, younger visitors, and those in organized groups spent less time at the museum. • Families with multiple income earners also tended to allocate less time.

	to understand visitor behaviour and provide insights for better museum management and marketing strategies.	Interviews: Data was collected through face-to-face interviews conducted at various times of day during weekdays and weekends. Data Analysis Method: -Zero-Truncated Negative Binomial (ZTNB) Regression Model - Statistical tests -Comparative analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bad weather conditions positively influenced the length of stay. • Entrance fees did not significantly affect time spent at the museum.
Smith, J. K., & Smith, L. F. (2001). Spending Time on Art. <i>Empirical Studies of the Arts</i> , 19(2), 229–236. https://doi.org/10.2190/5mqm-59jh-x21r-jn5j	<p>Research Problem: The study explores how museums can become more engaging and participative for Millennial and Gen Z audiences, addressing the disconnect between traditional museum practices and the cultural expectations of these younger generations.</p> <p>Research Objective:</p>	<p>Sample (Who/ How much/ Sampling Method):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Three museum professionals from Boijmans Van Beuningen and Kunstinstituut Melly. - Seven Millennial and Gen Z visitors (ages 23-29), all highly educated with varied cultural and social backgrounds. - Snowball sampling, facilitated through social 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Younger visitors desire participatory and interactive exhibits where they can co-create and personalize their experiences. • They prefer museums that address contemporary social issues and align with their values. • Technology and digital tools enhance

	<p>-To understand what Millennial and Gen Z audiences expect from museums.</p> <p>-To understand how museums currently approach these audiences.</p> <p>-To understand how concepts like "New Museology" and participatory practices can improve engagement and inclusivity for younger visitors.</p>	<p>media outreach and personal networks.</p> <p>Data Collection Method:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Semi-Structured Interviews - Field Visits <p>Data Analysis Method:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Thematic Analysis -Qualitative Coding 	<p>engagement, providing immersive, interactive experiences and accessible content.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional didactic models of museums are seen as exclusionary and uninviting for those with lower cultural capital. • Limited representation and lack of inclusivity discourage diverse audiences.
<p>(McSpadden, 2015)</p> <p>McSpadden, K. (2015, May 14). You now have a shorter attention span than a goldfish. <i>TIME</i>. https://time.com/3858309/attention-spans-goldfish/</p>			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • people now generally lose concentration after eight seconds • the average attention span dropped from 12 seconds to eight seconds

<p>(Marcus, 2022)</p> <p><i>Marcus, C. (2022, July). How to Grab Gen Z's Attention Span in 8 Seconds or Less. Colormatics</i></p>			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • short form videos less than 2mins • tell stories • clear and high quality videos • vertical videos with subtitle
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Note: Table shows the references, research problem, research objective, hypothesis, methodology (sampling/ data collection method/ data analysis method), and findings from the journal articles that are referred in the literature review.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the researcher describes the methodology used to address the research questions outlined in Chapter 1. It explains the research framework, the location of the study, the data collection methods, and the data analysis techniques employed to achieve the research objectives.

3.2 Research Framework

Figure 3.2.1

Research Framework Chart

Note: Figure 3.2.1 shows the flowchart of this research framework.

Based on figure 3.2.1, observations and secondary data will be used as the data collection method in this research. As the record of time spent by visitors looking and interacting with the selected exhibits in BCM is the main data, thus observation is the best method to be applied. This is because this experiment involves physical act, such as looking and interacting with exhibits. Furthermore, researcher have required advice from Dr. Norehan binti Zulkipli, a lecturer in the Faculty of Cognitive Sciences and

Human Development at University Malaysia Sarawak, who affirmed the appropriateness of utilizing observation as a data collection method for this research.

On the other hand, secondary data such as research journals and article are also used as references. The exist key findings will be used as the comparison for the data collected from BCM. After the data collecting process, quantitative and qualitative method will be applied to analyse the data. In the end of the analyzation, conclusions will be made.

3.3 Research location

Figure 3.3.1

Borneo Cultures Museum

Note: Figure above shows the building of Borneo Cultures Museum. Retrieved from <https://apicms.thestar.com.my/uploads/images/2024/05/14/2693559.webp>

This research will be taken in the Borneo Cultures Museum (BCM), Kuching, Sarawak. BCM is the largest museum complex in Malaysia, and second largest in Southeast Asia. Besides that, it is quite new since it started operating since March 2022.

Researchers choose BCM as the location of this research is because BCM have fulfilled this research's criteria where it includes static informational exhibit and visual interactive exhibit. Furthermore, researcher believe BCM attracts visitors from various age and background which increases the accuracy of this research.

Figure 3.3.2

Maps of the location of Borneo Cultures Museum

Note: Maps above show the location of Borneo Cultures Museum. Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/maps/place/Borneo+Cultures+Museum/>

3.3.1 Selected Exhibits for Observation

Figure 3.3.1.1

Static Informational Exhibit (Kelidieng Burial Pole)

Note: Figure above shows the Static Informational Exhibit, the Kelidieng Burial Pole.

Figure 3.3.1.2

Interactive Visual Exhibit (Puteri Santubong)

Note: Figure above shows the Interactive Visual Exhibit, Puteri Santubong.

For the static informational exhibit, the researcher chose the exhibit of the Kelidieng Burial Pole, which is a very important cultural object in the Melanau tribe. Additionally, the burial pole is engraved with special and meaningful motifs of the Melanau tribe. On the other hand, for interactive visual exhibit, researcher has chosen the 'Puteri Santubong' exhibit. This is because the exhibit allows visitors to engage with the display, such as pulling and pushing the LED to watch the animated video of Puteri Santubong's legend. Moreover, Puteri Santubong is a very significant and iconic figure in Sarawak. Thus, the researcher believes that both exhibits will attract the attention of foreign and local visitors, as the exhibits explain the story of Sarawak. Both exhibits are located on Level 3, Permanent Gallery: In Harmony with Nature of the Borneo Cultures Museum.

Figure 3.3.1.3

The Label of Static Informational Exhibit (Kelidieng Burial Pole)

Note: The label in the figure above explains the history of Kelidieng Burial Pole.

Figure 3.3.1.4

The Interpretive Label of Puteri Santubong Exhibit

Note: The label in the figure above explains the Puteri Santubong exhibit and provides instructions on how to use it.

3.4 Data Collection Method

Figure 3.4.1

Data Collection Method Chart

Note: Figure shows the method that will be used in this research.

Based on figure 3.4.1, two primary methods are employed in this research which is **observation** and **secondary data analysis**.

Observation enables the researcher to directly and in real time record visitor behaviour, such as the amount of time spent at exhibits and interaction. Researcher uses observation method to collect data **because it involves physical act, such as looking and interacting with exhibits**. The total sample size for this data collection is 172 visitors with 86 visitors for exhibit A (static informational exhibit), and 86 exhibit B (visual interactive exhibit). To prevent biasness, observer will choose and every third visitor who stepped into exhibit. If the number of visitors is low, choose the next visitor when observer is ready to start tracking. However, if the number of visitors is very high, observer will track every tenth visitor instead.

The sample size is calculated using G*Power with the effect size (Cohen's d): 0.5 (medium effect), Alpha (α): 0.05 (standard 95% confidence), Power (1 - β): 0.90

(90% power), and number of groups: 2 (for the static and interactive exhibit groups). **The reason population size isn't directly required for calculating sample size in this research is due to the nature of the statistical test that researcher is planning to use which is t-test for comparing two independent groups.**

Next, **secondary data**, on the other hand, involves utilizing pre-existing findings from research journal and articles to validate the new findings of current research.

Figure 3.4.2

Calculation Of Sample Size

$$t = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

Where:

- \bar{X}_1 and \bar{X}_2 are the sample means for group 1 and group 2.
- s_1^2 and s_2^2 are the sample variances for group 1 and group 2.
- n_1 and n_2 are the sample sizes for group 1 and group 2.

Note: Figure above shows the calculation formula on how to count and determine the sample size.

Figure 3.4.3

*Calculation of Sample Size Using G*Power*

Note: The G*Power software has counted 86 sample size number for each group.

Table 3.4.1*Terms and Definition of T-Test.*

Terms	Definition
Two-tailed t test	A statistical test used to determine if there is a significant difference between two groups, without specifying the direction of the difference.
Effect Size (Cohen's d: 0.5)	This represents the magnitude of the difference between the two groups. A medium effect size means the difference is noticeable and likely meaningful but not extremely large.
Alpha (α : 0.05)	This is the significance level, indicating the threshold for rejecting the null hypothesis. At 0.05, there's a 5% risk of concluding there is a difference when none exists (Type I error).
Power (1 - β : 0.90)	This indicates the probability of correctly detecting a true difference if one exists. A power of 0.90 means there's a 90% chance of avoiding a Type II error (failing to detect a real difference).
Number of Groups (2)	This indicates the comparison is between two independent groups one experiencing static exhibits and the other interactive exhibits.

3.4.1 Observation

Figure 3.4.1.1

Data Collection Method Flowchart

Note: The Flowchart of Data Collection Process. The process is according to Voorde (2023) from ‘Exploring Engagement in Science Museums: A Comparative Study of Static and Interactive Exhibitions’.

Figure 3.4.1.2

Example of Observation Distance

Note: The illustration show the example of observation distance between observer and the visitors when looking at the selected exhibits.

Based on figure 3.541.2, it shows the flowchart of the observation process. Firstly, observer need identifying the observation space of the exhibit. This helps to define the boundaries of the observation area which makes it easier for the observer to know when a visitor steps into the designated space. Then, observer will stay 3 meters away from the exhibit space just like figure 3.4.3 to ensure the physical act of visitors can be observed clearly. Next, once the visitor goes into the exhibition space, the observer can immediately start the timer to begin tracking their interaction with the exhibit. During the observation process, the time spent and interaction of visitors in the exhibit space will be tracked. The information of visitors will not be recorded as researcher does not want to interrupt the attention of visitors during the exhibit visit. It is concerned that the actions of the visitors might not be natural after knowing they are being observed. Thirdly, once the visitor stops looking, interacting and step out of the exhibition space, the stopwatch will be stopped immediately. Fourthly, observer will record the time spent and interaction of visitors in the observation template. After completing observing 86 visitors per exhibit, researcher will count the average time spent. Then, the data will be analysed and be concluded.

Observer will choose and every third visitor who stepped into exhibit. If the number of visitors is low, choose the next visitor when observer is ready to start tracking. However, if the number of visitors is very high, observer will track every tenth visitor instead. This process is to prevent biasness.

The observation process:

1. Observer draws a line within the selected exhibits.
2. Observer will sit 3meters away from the selected exhibits.
3. Stopwatch will be started when the selected visitor stepped into and start looking, interacting with the exhibit.
4. Stop stopwatch when visitor stop looking, interacting and stepped out of the exhibit.
5. Record the time in the observation template.
6. Count the average time spent by visitors when the targeted numbers of visitors achieved.

Table 3.4.1.1*Example of Observation Template*

Exhibit			
Observer name			
No of visitors	Date	Time spent (Total time spent from starting to ending of looking at the exhibit)	Interactions (Visitors interact with the exhibit) Tick
1	dd/mm/yy	...sec	/
2		...sec	
3		...sec	
4		...sec	
5		...sec	
6		...sec	
7		...sec	
8		...sec	
9		...sec	
10		...sec	
11		...sec	
12		...sec	
13		...sec	
14		...sec	
15		...sec	
16		...sec	
17		...sec	
18		...sec	
19		...sec	
20		...sec	
Total			
Formula		Total time spent / Total visitors = Average time spent (Mean)	
Mean (sec)			

3.4.2 Secondary Data

In this research, the researcher has extracted key findings from online journals and publications to serve as references. The key findings are used to be the comparison for the data collected from Borneo Cultures Museum.

The secondary data used in this study have helped the researcher gain a deeper understanding of critical concepts such as attention span and museum learning, enriching the theoretical framework and providing context for the primary data collected.

3.5 Data Analysis Method

Figure 3.5.1

Data Analysis Method Chart

Note: Data analysis method flowchart

Based on the figure above, both quantitative and qualitative analyses will be used in this research. For quantitative analysis, two primary methods will be employed which are descriptive statistics and comparative analysis.

3.5.1 Quantitative Analysis

Initially, descriptive statistics will be applied to summarize the data, focusing on key measures such as the average time spent by visitors at each exhibit type (static versus interactive) and the frequency of interactions with each exhibit. This will give an overview of visitor behaviour and provide a foundation for comparing the exhibits.

After this, comparative analysis will be conducted using an independent samples t-test, a statistical method used to compare the means of two independent groups (i.e., visitors interacting with the static exhibit and visitors interacting with the interactive exhibit). This will determine whether there are significant differences in the time spent and the frequency of interactions at the two exhibit types.

The test assumes the two groups are independent, and the results will help identify if one exhibit type leads to significantly more engagement than the other. The sample size of 172 visitors, split equally between the two exhibit types, ensures that the study has enough power (90%) to detect meaningful differences, with a medium effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.5$) and a 95% confidence level.

Figure 3.5.1.1

Example Bar Chart Of Data Comparison

Note: After the raw data is tabulated and analysed, bar chart as above will be inserted to show the data comparison.

3.6 Conclusion

The purpose of the present research was to have a look at how various kinds of exhibits traditional, digital, and interactive influence the attention spans of the museum visitors in Malaysia. The research by studying the behaviour of visitors in the Borneo cultures Museum (BCM) casts light on the impact of exhibit design on the length of time that visitors spend at the displays. The findings indicate the need to be aware of the audiences' attention span in contemporary museums as the application of digital and interactive technologies are increasingly becoming frequent. The components have the potential to improve interaction especially in times when concentration can be easily divided.

This research also indicates the requirement of the balanced approach, which would require combining the traditional and modern features of exhibits to keep the visitors interested and better engage others. This study bridges the gap of the body of knowledge as it has considered a particular scenario of Malaysian museums and thus provides usable information to curators and designers.

Overall, the case study offers a premise to future studies on the ways technology may enhance the museum visit. It provides the chance to study other types of exhibits, to increase the size of a sample, and to study long-term impact of visitor involvement with the learning and general museum experience.

Finally, the research will reveal the effect of exhibit design in attention and interaction. Museums such as BCM will use the findings to establish better contact to the visitors and come up with a memorable experience that is not only informative but also interesting.

Table 3.6.1*Table of Research Methodology*

Research Objective	Collection Method	Sample (How Many / Why / Who / Sampling Method)	Data Analysis Method
RO1: To identify the average attention span of visitors when visiting museum exhibits.	-Observation	-172 visitors (86 for static exhibits, 86 for interactive exhibits). -Chosen randomly using an interval method at entry points (e.g., every 3rd or 10th visitor depending on foot traffic).	Quantitative: Descriptive statistics, Independent Samples t-test. Qualitative: Content analysis of secondary data.
RO2: To analyse how interactive and digital elements in exhibits impact the attention span of visitors.	-Observation -Secondary Data	-172 visitors (86 for static exhibits, 86 for interactive exhibits). -Secondary data from prior research / publications	Quantitative: Independent Samples t-test for comparisons. Qualitative: Content analysis of secondary data.
RO3: To document the types of content that are most effective in capturing the visitors' attention in a museum display.	-Observation	-172 visitors -Observed interactions with different exhibit types -Random interval sampling	Quantitative: Comparative analysis (e.g., frequency of interactions per content type).

Note: The table show the research methodology, collection method, sample and data analysis method.

CHAPTER 4

DATA COLLECTION

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, researcher shows the collected data of the attention span of visitors spent on both selected interactive and static exhibits in Borneo Cultures Museum (BCM). Researcher have successfully completed the data collection within 3 days which are 19, 20 and 21 April 2025. The selected exhibit are as follows:

Figure 4.1.1

Interactive Visual Exhibit (Puteri Santubong)

Note: Picture shows two visitors interacting with the Puteri Santubong exhibit

Figure 4.1.2

Static Informational Exhibit (Kelidieng Burial Pole)

Note: Picture shows two visitors interacting with the Puteri Santubong exhibit

Figure 4.1.3

Kelidieng Burial Pole and The Observing Corner

Note: The corner with red line is where observer (Ng Yen Yen) sat to collect data.

4.2 Data Collected

4.2.1 Interactive Visual Exhibit 'Puteri Santubong'

Table 4.2.1.1

The Raw Data Of Visitor's Time Spent On Puteri Santubong Exhibit

Exhibit	Puteri Santubong		
Observer	Ng Yen Yen		
No of visitors	Date	Time spent (Total time spent from starting to ending of looking at the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick
1	17/04/25	149	/
2		120	/
3		120	/
4		60	/
5		207	/
6		50	
7		169	/
8		144	/
9		320	/
10		157	/
11		120	/
12		48	/
13		68	/
14		188	/
15		91	
16		428	/
17		60	/
18		157	/
19		34	
20		7	
21		29	/
22		50	/
23		169	/
24		320	/
25		188	/
26		9	
27		11	
28		133	/

29	19/04/25	212	/
30		174	/
31		116	/
32		32	
33		140	/
34		120	/
35		290	/
36		128	/
37		185	/
38		221	/
39		92	/
40		152	/
41		243	/
42		141	/
43		80	/
44		67	/
45		143	/
46		179	/
47		154	/
48		190	/
49		121	/
50		189	/
51		230	/
52		194	/
53		155	/
54		69	/
55		155	/
56		138	/
57	20/04/25	144	/
58		209	/
59		144	/
60		40	
61		29	
62		92	/
63		70	
64		243	/
65		149	/
66		148	/
67		145	/
68		230	/
69		156	/
70		118	/
71		14	
72		321	/
73		178	/
74		136	/
75		135	
76		148	

77		196	/
78		199	/
79		58	/
80		102	/
81		177	/
82		244	/
83		27	
84		132	/
85		263	/
86		157	/
Total		12320	72
Formula		Total time spent / Total visitors = Average time spent (Mean)	
Mean (sec)		$12320 / 86 = 143.256$ $= 143 \text{ sec}$	

Note: The table shows the raw data of Puteri Santubong exhibit collected by observer (Ng Yen Yen) on 3 different days. The mean (average time spent by 86 visitors) is counted as well and written at the bottom of the table. The hand written raw data will be inserted in the appendices.

4.2.2 Static Informational Exhibit (Kelidieng Burial Pole)

Table 4.2.2.1

The Raw Data Of Visitor's Time Spent On Kelidieng Burial Pole Exhibit

Exhibit	Kelidieng Burial Pole		
Observer	Ng Yen Yen		
No of visitors	Date	Time spent (Total time spent from starting to ending of looking at the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick
1	17/04/25	149	/
2		120	/
3		120	/
4		60	/
5		207	/
6		50	
7		169	/
8		144	/
9		320	/
10		157	/
11		120	/
12		48	/
13		68	/
14		188	/
15		91	
16		428	/
17		60	/
18		157	/
19		34	
20		7	
21		29	/
22		50	/
23		169	/
24		320	/
25		188	/
26		9	
27	19/04/25	11	
28		133	/

29		212	/
30		174	/
31		116	/
32		32	
33		140	/
34		120	/
35		290	/
36		128	/
37		185	/
38		221	/
39		92	/
40		152	/
41		243	/
42		141	/
43		80	/
44		67	/
45		143	/
46		179	/
47		154	/
48		190	/
49		121	/
50		189	/
51		230	/
52		194	/
53		155	/
54		69	/
55		155	/
56		138	/
57		144	/
58		209	/
59		144	/
60		40	
61		29	
62		92	/
63		70	
64		243	/
65		149	/
66		148	/
67		145	/
68		230	/
69	20/04/25	156	/
70		118	/
71		14	
72		321	/
73		178	/
74		136	/
75		135	
76		148	

77		196	/
78		199	/
79		58	/
80		102	/
81		177	/
82		244	/
83		27	
84		132	/
85		263	/
86		149	/
Total		2416	18
Formula		Total time spent / Total visitors = Average time spent (Mean)	
Mean (sec)		2416 / 86 = 28.09302326 = 28 sec	

Note: The table shows the raw data of Kelidieng Burial Pole exhibit collected by observer (Ng Yen Yen) on 3 different days. The mean (average time spent by 86 visitors) is counted as well and written at the bottom of the table. The hand written raw data will be inserted in the appendices.

4.3 Data Analysis

4.3.1 Average Time Spent Between Two Exhibits

Table 4.3.1.1

Table of Average Time Spent Between Two Exhibits

Exhibit	Total time spent (sec)	Average time spent (sec)
Interactive Visual Exhibit (Puteri Santubong)	12320	143
Static Visual Exhibit (Kelidieng Burial Pole)	2416	28

Note: The calculated total time spent (sec) and average time spent (sec) of both exhibit are tabulated into the table above.

Figure 4.3.1.1

Pie Chart of Average Time Spent

Average Time Spent (sec)

Note: The data of the average time spent by visitors in both exhibit are transformed into a pie chart for better understanding.

Based on pie chart 4.3.1.1, it shows the average time spent of visitors on both interactive visual exhibit (Puteri Santubong) and static informational

exhibit (Kelidieng Burial Pole). The Puteri Santubong exhibit has taken 83.63% of the pie chart with average of 143sec. On the other hand, the Kelidieng Burial Pole exhibit consists 16.37% of the pie chart with average of 28sec. This clearly shows that interactive visual exhibits gain more attention of the museum visitors.

4.3.2 Engagement's Categories

Table 4.3.2.1

Engagement's Categories

Category	Time Spent (seconds)
Brief Engagement	≤ 60
Short Engagement	61 – 300
Moderate Engagement	301 – 900
High Engagement	> 900

Note: The calculated total time spent (sec) and average time spent (sec) is tabulated into the table above.

Table 4.3.2.2

The Interactive Visual Exhibit (Puteri Santubong) Engagement Totals with Time Ranges

Category	Time range	Total visitors
Brief Engagement	≤ 60 seconds	16
Short Engagement	61 – 300 seconds	66
Moderate Engagement	301 – 900 seconds	4

Note: The 86 visitors' time spent on Puteri Santubong exhibit are divided into different engagement categories with different time range.

Table 4.3.2.3

Static Informational Exhibit (Kelidieng Burial Pole) Engagement Totals with Time Ranges

Category	Time range	Total visitors
Brief Engagement	≤ 60 seconds	82
Short Engagement	61 – 300 seconds	4

Note: The 86 visitors' time spent on Puteri Santubong exhibit are divided into different engagement categories with different time range.

Figure 4.3.2.1

Visitors' Engagement Totals by Time Range

Note: The data of both the exhibit's engagement totals with time ranges are transformed into bar chart to see the differences clearly.

Based on bar chart above, there are three categories of engagement. The first category is brief engagement which range exact or lesser than 60 seconds. The second category is short engagement which is within 61 to 300 seconds while the third category, moderate engagement is 301 to 900 seconds.

If there are any engagement more than 900 seconds, it is considered as high engagement. Unfortunately, based on the data collected by researcher, there are no visitors who engage with the selected exhibits more than 900 seconds which is 15 minutes.

For brief engagement, the interactive visual exhibit (Puteri Santubong) attracted 16 visitors, while the static informational exhibit (Kelidieng Burial Pole) saw a higher engagement with 82 visitors. Next, short engagement, Puteri Santubong exhibit records engagement of 66 visitors while Kelidieng Burial Pole exhibits have lower engagement of 4 visitors. Thirdly, moderate engagement only records 4 visitors engagement for Puteri Santubong Exhibit while Kelidieng Burial Pole exhibit have none.

From this exhibit engagement totals by time range bar chart, we can clearly see that interactive visual exhibit (Puteri Santubong) receives higher and more attention compared to static informational exhibit (Kelidieng Burial Pole). This is because researcher observe and collected 3 categories of engagement ranges for Puteri Santubong exhibit while Kelidieng Burial Pole only got 2. Furthermore, Puteri Santubong exhibit's highest engagement collected, are 66 visitors and they falls in the short engagement category, which is within 61 to 300 seconds, 16 visitors in the brief engagement category, and lowest, 16 visitors in the moderate engagement which is 301 to 900 seconds.

4.3.3 Exhibits Interaction Timetable

Table 4.3.3.1

Visitor's Interaction Count, and Interaction Time Spent

Exhibit	Interaction count (individual)	Total time spent (sec)	Average time spent (min)
Static Informational Exhibit (Burial Pole Kelidieng)	18	614	0.57
Visual Interactive Exhibit (Puteri Santubong)	72	11623	2.69

Note: This table shows the total visitors who interacted with the selected exhibits. The time spent interacting with the selected exhibit is recorded in the data as well. The time spent will then divided with the number of visitors to count the mean (average) in both seconds and minutes.

Figure 4.3.3.1

Bar Chart of Visitor's Interaction Count, and Interaction Time Spent

Note: The exhibit interaction count and time spent of visitors on both exhibit is transformed into bar chart to show the difference.

The bar chart above shows the number and average time spent by the visitors that interacted with both selected exhibits. Out of total 172 visitors, the visitors that interacted with the Kelidieng Burial Pole, are 18 visitors while Puteri Santubong are 72 visitors. Based on table 4.4.3, the total time spent by the 18 visitors that interacted with Kelidieng Burial Pole is 614 seconds while the Puteri Santubong exhibit is 11,623 seconds which is equivalent to 10.23 minutes and 193.72 minutes.

The average time spent on Kelidieng Burial Pole exhibit is 0.57 minutes while Puteri Santubong exhibit is 2.69 minutes.

From this, we can clear see that interactive-enhanced exhibit attracts more interactions from visitors compared to static exhibits. From researcher's observation, visitors seldom take pictures, videos of the exhibit, touch, push and pull the LED screen of the Puteri Santubong exhibit while visitors only take pictures and touch the Kelidieng Burial Pole exhibit. The limitations of storytelling, animations, and interacting elements causes the lack of interest from visitors thus happen the contrast between the two exhibits.

4.4 Theoretical Framework

The results of the analysis done by the researcher correspond well with psychological theories as to why the interactive exhibit, Puteri Santubong drew more attention and involvement as compared to the Kelidieng Burial Pole exhibit which was non-interactive. This evidence confirms the fact that the interactive exhibit earned so much time and attention compared to time spent on Kelidieng Burial Pole which is only 28 seconds on average. Such dissimilarity in engagement can be adjudged with regard to some of the major psychological theories, such as the flow, multisensory engagement, intrinsic motivation, cognitive guidance theory, and the theory of object-based attention.

4.4.1 Flow Theory

As Barton et al. (2020) highlight, the concept of "flow" refers to a state of complete immersion and focus that is fostered by providing an optimal level of cognitive challenge. Puteri Santubong's interactive features offer a tailored challenge to visitors, keeping them engaged for a longer time. The data supports this theory, as visitors spent more time on the interactive exhibit, with a higher proportion of visitors (66 visitors) falling into the short engagement category (61 to 300 seconds). In contrast, Kelidieng Burial Pole saw fewer visitors engaging within the same time range. This aligns with the idea that interactive exhibits induce a flow state, where visitors remain deeply involved without being distracted.

4.4.2 Multisensory Engagement Theory

According to Leopoldi (n.d.), interactive exhibits like Puteri Santubong stimulate multiple sensory pathways, which increase emotional and behavioral engagement. The researcher's observation that visitors interacted physically with the LED screen of Puteri Santubong, such as touching, pushing, and pulling, supports the theory that multisensory engagement heightens visitor involvement. In contrast, Kelidieng Burial Pole lacked such interactive features, leading to a more passive experience with minimal physical interaction, which corresponds to the lower engagement time observed in the data. This supports the idea that multisensory experiences create more vivid and emotionally resonant engagements, leading to heightened attention and participation.

4.4.3 Cognitive Guidance Theory

As Leopoldi (n.d.) discusses, the interactive design of Puteri Santubong reduces cognitive overload by presenting information in digestible, dynamic segments. The researcher's analysis indicates that Puteri Santubong attracted visitors to engage across all three categories (brief, short, and moderate engagement), while Kelidieng Burial Pole only saw visitors fall into two categories. This suggests that the interactive design made it easier for visitors to engage without feeling overwhelmed, unlike the static exhibit, which failed to capture prolonged attention. This supports the theory that interactive designs reduce cognitive overload by breaking down information into manageable pieces.

4.4.4 Intrinsic Motivation Theory

Voorde (2023) emphasizes the concept of intrinsic motivation, which drives visitors to engage more deeply with exhibits that offer self-directed exploration. Puteri Santubong provided a more engaging and personal experience, which encouraged visitors to spend more time interacting with it. The researcher's analysis of visitor behaviour, including their physical interaction with the exhibit and the higher number of visitors in the short engagement category, supports the theory that interactive experiences tap into visitors' curiosity and intrinsic motivation to explore. This aligns with the idea that personal investment and curiosity enhance engagement and prolong attention.

4.4.5 Object-Based Attention Theory

As Gibson (1994) and Scholl & Department of Psychology, Yale University (2000) note, the object-based attention theory posits that attention is allocated to whole objects, rather than just spatial regions. Puteri Santubong, with its interactive elements, encourages visitors to focus on the entire object (the exhibit) as an integrated entity, enhancing attention and engagement.

Visitors are likely more invested in exploring the whole object as a single unit, rather than as disparate parts, which contrasts with the static Kelidieng Burial Pole, where attention may have been split across regions without an integrated object-based focus.

To sum up, the findings made by the researcher substantiate various psychological theories clarifying the greater interest in the interactive Puteri Santubong exhibit compared with the fixed Kelidieng Burial Pole exhibit. Interactive design of Puteri Santubong promoted flow, multisensory interactions, diminished cognitive workload and engaged intrinsic motivation, which was seen in the increase in visitor interaction as viewed in data results. Furthermore, the object-based attention theory further describes how attention was maintained because of the interactive and integrated properties of the exhibit. These results correlate with psychological studies that interactive and immersive displays tend to be better at attention maintenance and a more profound stimulus response (Barton et al., 2020; Leopoldi, M., n.d.; Voorde, B. M., 2023; Gibson, 1994; Scholl & Department of Psychology, Yale University, 2000)

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Discussion

Based on the data analysis, the discussion of the research findings will be divided into 3 sections as follows:

- i. To identify the average attention span of visitors when visiting museum exhibits.
- ii. To analyse how interactive and digital elements in exhibits impact the attention span of visitors.
- iii. To document the types of content that are most effective in capturing the visitors' attention in a museum display.

5.1.1 Average Attention Span of Visitors in Museum Exhibits

The average attention span of visitors in the two exhibits, *Puteri Santubong* (interactive visual exhibit) and *Kelidieng Burial Pole* (static informational exhibit), shows a clear distinction. Visitors spent an average of 143 seconds (approximately 2.39 minutes) on the *Puteri Santubong* exhibit, compared to only 28 seconds on the *Kelidieng Burial Pole* exhibit. This difference is consistent with the principles of flow theory, which suggests that interactive exhibits, like *Puteri Santubong*, provide the right level of cognitive challenge to keep visitors engaged (Barton et al., 2020). The higher time spent on *Puteri Santubong* indicates that the interactive features kept visitors immersed, inducing a state of flow, where visitors were deeply engaged with the content and remained focused for a longer duration.

5.1.2 Impact of Interactive and Digital Elements on Attention Span

The data reveals that the interactive *Puteri Santubong* exhibit garnered significantly more attention than the static *Kelidieng Burial Pole* exhibit. This finding is supported by multisensory engagement theory, which posits that interactive exhibits stimulate multiple sensory pathways, leading

to greater emotional and behavioral engagement (Leopoldi, n.d.). In the case of *Puteri Santubong*, visitors engaged with the LED screens through touch and physical interaction, which heightened their involvement with the exhibit. This multisensory experience aligns with Leopoldi's argument that sensory-rich environments lead to deeper emotional connections and increased attention. On the other hand, the *Kelidieng Burial Pole* exhibit, which lacked interactive elements, led to minimal physical interaction, resulting in lower engagement. Therefore, the absence of multisensory stimulation in the static exhibit contributed to the shorter attention span observed in visitors.

Furthermore, cognitive guidance theory supports the idea that the interactive design of *Puteri Santubong* reduced cognitive overload by presenting information in easily digestible, dynamic segments (Leopoldi, n.d.). The *Puteri Santubong* exhibit successfully engaged visitors in all three categories of engagement (brief, short, and moderate), whereas *Kelidieng Burial Pole* only attracted visitors in the brief engagement category. This suggests that interactive exhibits reduce the cognitive load on visitors by offering clear, manageable pieces of information, making it easier for them to remain focused and engaged for longer periods.

5.1.3 Most Effective Content Types in Capturing Visitor Attention

The content of the *Puteri Santubong* exhibit was more effective in capturing visitors' attention compared to the *Kelidieng Burial Pole* exhibit. This finding aligns with intrinsic motivation theory, which emphasizes that exhibits offering opportunities for self-directed exploration foster deeper engagement (Voorde, 2023). The *Puteri Santubong* exhibit encouraged visitors to actively interact with the content, fulfilling their intrinsic motivation to explore and learn. The data supports this, as 66 visitors spent between 61 to 300 seconds on the interactive exhibit, demonstrating a high level of engagement driven by personal curiosity and interest. In contrast, the *Kelidieng Burial Pole* exhibit, which did not offer such opportunities for exploration, saw fewer visitors engaging with the content for extended periods.

Moreover, the object-based attention theory proposed by Gibson (1994) and Scholl & Department of Psychology, Yale University (2000), further explains why visitors spent more time with *Puteri Santubong*. According to this theory, attention is drawn to the object, rather than to separate parts of the exhibit. The interactive elements of *Puteri Santubong* created an integrated experience where visitors focused on the exhibit as a single object, enhancing attention and engagement. In contrast, the static nature of *Kelidieng Burial Pole* led to a more fragmented focus, with visitors attending to different parts of the exhibit without the same level of cohesive engagement.

5.1 Limitations of the Study

While this study offers valuable insights into visitor engagement with both interactive and static exhibits, there are several limitations that should be considered. First, the sample size of 86 visitors is relatively small, which may not fully represent the broader museum-going population. Future research should aim to include a larger and more heterogeneous sample to enhance the generalizability of the results. Additionally, this study focused on only two exhibits within a single museum. Expanding the research to involve a wider variety of exhibits across multiple museums, as well as diverse cultural contexts, could provide a more comprehensive understanding of visitor engagement patterns.

Another limitation of this study is the reliance on observed behaviour. While visitor engagement was measured by time spent and the number of interactions, the study did not account for factors such as visitor motivation, prior knowledge, or emotional reactions. Future research could incorporate methods such as surveys, interviews, or online tracking tools to capture deeper insights into why visitors are drawn to certain exhibits and how their cognitive and emotional states influence their engagement. Additionally, the use of only visual observations by the researcher may have resulted in missing subtle aspects of visitor interactions, such as body language or multisensory engagement that might not have been immediately apparent. The inclusion of additional technologies or devices to track these interactions could offer a more detailed and nuanced understanding of visitor behaviour.

Another notable limitation is the absence of demographic data, such as the age of visitors, which could have provided more specific insights into how different age groups engage with interactive versus static exhibits. Age may play a significant role in how visitors relate to exhibits, with younger individuals possibly being more inclined towards interactive experiences, while older visitors may prefer static displays. Future research could benefit from collecting demographic data to better understand the impact of age and other characteristics on visitor engagement.

Finally, this study analysed visitor engagement at a single point in time. Longitudinal research could offer more valuable insights into how visitor engagement

evolves over repeated exposures to exhibits. For example, studying whether the novelty of interactive exhibits diminishes after the first visit or whether visitors continue to respond enthusiastically over time could help museums create exhibits that remain engaging over longer periods. By observing visitor behaviour over time, future studies could explore how engagement evolves and how interactive elements can maintain their effectiveness in sustaining attention and interest through multiple visits.

5.2 Future Research Directions

Future research should explore the specific impacts of various interactive technologies, including virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and gamified content, on visitor engagement in museum settings. Understanding how different interactive features affect attention span and depth of engagement can help curators design more effective and tailored exhibition strategies. For example, the integration of VR and AR may significantly enhance the visitor experience by offering immersive and visually stimulating ways to interact with exhibition content. Similarly, gamification elements such as quizzes, challenges, or narrative-driven interactions may promote deeper engagement by personalizing the visitor experience and encouraging prolonged attention at exhibits.

In addition, future studies should examine the role of social factors such as group dynamics, peer presence, or family interactions in shaping visitor engagement. Museums are often experienced as social environments rather than purely individual ones, and the presence of others can influence both the duration and quality of interactions with exhibits. Exploring how these social contexts affect engagement could help inform exhibit design strategies that cater to both group visitors and individuals.

Another promising avenue is longitudinal research that monitors visitor engagement over an extended period. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of how repeated exposure to interactive exhibits influences visitor behaviour and sustained interest. For instance, while interactive features may initially attract visitors due to their novelty, repeated visits could result in reduced engagement as the features

become familiar. Longitudinal studies can help determine whether engagement levels are sustained, decline, or require regular updates and enhancements to remain effective.

Tracking engagement across multiple visits or different seasons would also provide insight into the long-term effectiveness of interactive elements. Researchers could investigate whether high levels of engagement observed in the early stages of an exhibition diminish over time or whether minor content updates can sustain or even increase interest. Such findings would be useful for museums that aim to maintain dynamic and appealing exhibitions for repeat visitors.

Moreover, longitudinal studies can be designed to assess how interactive and static exhibits contribute to knowledge retention and long-term educational outcomes. By observing repeated visitor interactions, researchers may determine whether interactive experiences support deeper learning compared to traditional static displays. Museums might also consider rotating content or introducing new digital components periodically. Evaluating the impact of such changes could offer valuable guidance in planning exhibitions that continuously engage and educate their audiences.

5.3 Broader Implications

The results of this research hold significant implications for museum curators and exhibit designers. The evidence strongly supports the hypothesis that interactive and immersive exhibits are more effective in maintaining visitor interest and engagement compared to static informational displays. This finding underscores the need for museums to adapt their exhibit designs in response to the evolving expectations of visitors. Modern audiences are increasingly seeking dynamic and participatory experiences, and museums must meet these expectations by incorporating interactive digital elements. Neglecting to include such elements risks alienating contemporary visitors, who expect both educational and immersive museum experiences.

These findings also have broader implications for the field of educational psychology. The study emphasizes how museums can leverage psychological theories, such as flow theory, multisensory engagement theory, and intrinsic motivation theory, to enhance visitor engagement and learning opportunities. By applying these psychological frameworks, museums can create exhibits that not only captivate visitors aesthetically but also promote deeper emotional and cognitive interaction with the content.

For example, flow theory suggests that exhibits should be designed to match visitors' skill levels with appropriate cognitive challenges, maintaining engagement without overwhelming them (Barton et al., 2020). Multisensory engagement theory highlights the importance of incorporating sensory experiences that foster stronger emotional connections and encourage longer-lasting attention (Leopoldi, n.d.). Intrinsic motivation theory, on the other hand, suggests that self-directed exploration, where visitors can interact with exhibits at their own pace, enhances engagement by tapping into their natural curiosity (Voorde, 2023). These psychological theories collectively suggest that exhibits designed with these principles in mind are more likely to offer a meaningful and enriching experience.

Ultimately, the findings of this study emphasize the growing importance of interactive and immersive exhibits in facilitating learning and engagement. Museum curators and designers can use these insights to create exhibits that not only capture

attention but also encourage active participation and self-guided learning. By incorporating interactive, psychologically informed design elements into exhibits, museums can enhance both educational outcomes and visitor satisfaction, ensuring their relevance in an ever-changing cultural landscape.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study underscores the significant role that interactive and digital elements play in enhancing visitor engagement and attention within museum exhibits. The data reveals that the interactive *Puteri Santubong* exhibit, which incorporated multimedia features and provided opportunities for hands-on interaction, effectively captivated visitors for longer periods compared to the static *Kelidieng Burial Pole* exhibit. This finding aligns with psychological theories, including **flow theory**, **multisensory engagement theory**, **cognitive guidance theory**, **intrinsic motivation theory**, and **object-based attention theory**, all of which help explain how interactive exhibits foster deeper engagement and sustained attention. These theories highlight the importance of engaging visitors through dynamic and immersive experiences that encourage exploration and interaction.

Despite the valuable insights offered by this study, its limitations, such as the small sample size and the focus on a single museum, suggest that future research should explore a wider range of exhibits and a more diverse set of visitor profiles. Further studies could expand on the findings by incorporating a larger sample size, examining different types of exhibits across various museums, and investigating how visitor characteristics, such as age and prior knowledge, influence engagement.

Nevertheless, the findings of this research provide important implications for museum curators, educators, and exhibit designers, emphasizing the critical need for interactive and immersive experiences in fostering meaningful engagement and enhancing learning outcomes. As museums continue to evolve, understanding the factors that sustain visitor attention and engagement will be essential in creating exhibits that are both educational and enjoyable. By integrating interactive, digitally enhanced elements into exhibits, museums can better cater to the evolving needs and expectations of modern visitors, ensuring a more impactful and memorable museum experience.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A : Conversation on FYP research methodology enquiry with Associate Professor Dr. Norehan binti Zulkiply, a cognitive psychology expert.

Figure 6.0

Figure 6.1

APPENDIX B : Conversation with Sarawak Museum Department on asking permission to do data collection in Borneo Cultures Museum.

Figure 6.2

Figure 6.3

Figure 6.4

APPENDIX C : Conversation with Cik Asnida, staff of Sarawak Museum Department regarding the day of data collection.

Figure 6.5

Figure 6.6

APPENDIX D: Application letter to do data collection (observation) in Borneo Cultures Museum.

Fakulti Seni Gunaan dan Kreatif
Faculty of Applied And Creative Arts

UNIMAS/NC-20.03/04-29/01 Jld. 6 (45)

7 Februari 2025

Pengarah
Jabatan Muzium Sarawak
Jalan P.Ramlee
93400, Kuching
Sarawak
(u.p: Puan Nancy Haji Jolhi)

Puan,

Pengesahan Sebagai Pelajar dan Permohonan Membuat Kajian Untuk Projek Tahun Akhir

Dengan segala hormatnya perkara di atas dirujuk.

Dengan ini disahkan bahawa pelajar seperti berikut adalah merupakan pelajar dari Program Pengurusan Seni, Fakulti Seni Gunaan dan Kreatif, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak. Pelajar ini sedang dalam proses menyiapkan satu tugas untuk kursus GKP3353 Projek Tahun Akhir I. Tugas ini adalah salah satu daripada keperluan dan syarat untuk lulus subjek tersebut dan ianya bertujuan akademik semata-mata.

Sehubungan itu, pihak kami memohon kerjasama pihak Puan agar dapat memberi kebenaran kepada pelajar ini untuk membuat penyelidikan di agensi Puan bagi menjalankan projek tahun akhir beliau. Untuk makluman, kajian ini akan dijalankan secara bersemuka. Butiran pelajar adalah seperti berikut:-

Nama Pelajar : Ng Yen Yen (No. Matrik: 84840)
Nama Penyelia Kursus : Dr. Rahah Haji Hasan (082-581333)
Tajuk Kajian : Visitor Attention Span and Museum Learning:
The Influence of Exhibit Type and Interactivity

Sukacita sekiranya pihak Puan dapat meluluskan permohonan pelajar tersebut. Sekiranya ada sebarang pertanyaan, sila hubungi pensyarah yang berkenaan di talian seperti yang dinyatakan atau menghubungi terus pelajar tersebut di talian 016-7435033. Di atas pertimbangan dan kerjasama yang pihak Puan berikan, saya dahului dengan ucapan ribuan terima kasih.

Sekian.

Yang benar

Shaheera Athira Binti Shaeedun
Penolong Pendaftar

APPENDIX E: Application letter for free entry to Borneo Cultures Museum for final year project's data collection.

Fakulti Seni Gunaan dan Kreatif
Faculty of Applied And Creative Arts

UNIMAS/NC-20.03/04-29/01 Jld. 6 (46)

10 Februari 2025

Pengarah
Jabatan Muzium Sarawak
Jalan P. Ramlee
93400 Kuching
Sarawak
(u.p: Puan Nancy Haji Jolhi)

Puan,

Permohonan Tajaan Tiket Masuk Percuma Untuk Tujuan Penyelidikan

Dengan segala hormatnya perkara di atas dirujuk.

Dengan ini disahkan bahawa Saudari Ng Yen Yen adalah merupakan pelajar dari Program Pengurusan Seni, Fakulti Seni Gunaan dan Kreatif, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak yang sedang menjalankan penyelidikan bertajuk "*Visitor Attention Span and Museum Learning: The Influence of Exhibit Type and Interactivity.*" Kajian ini bertujuan untuk mengkaji tempoh perhatian pengunjung serta bagaimana jenis pameran dan tahap interaktiviti mempengaruhi pengalaman pembelajaran di muzium.

Sehubungan dengan itu, pihak kami ingin memohon tajaan tiket masuk percuma kepada pelajar ini bagi membolehkan beliau untuk menjalankan pemerhatian dan pengumpulan data di *Borneo Cultures Museum*. Diharap hasil penyelidikan beliau nanti dapat memberikan manfaat kepada pihak muzium dalam memahami dan meningkatkan pengalaman pembelajaran para pengunjung.

Sukacita sekiranya pihak puan dapat mempertimbangkan permohonan ini. Sekiranya ada sebarang pertanyaan, sila hubungi pensyarah Dr. Rahah Haji Hasan (082-581333) atau menghubungi pelajar tersebut di talian 016-7435033. Di atas pertimbangan dan kerjasama yang pihak Puan berikan saya dahului dengan ucapan ribuan terima kasih.

Sekian.

Yang benar

Shaheera Athira Binti Shaeedun
Penolong Pendaftar

APPENDIX F : Observation template by Voorde (2023) from ‘Exploring Engagement in Science Museums: A Comparative Study of Static and Interactive Exhibitions’.

Participant	Time period <i>Starting and ending time of checking out the exhibition</i>	Recording Interaction <i>Participant interacted with the exhibition (e.g., manipulating exhibition components, reading exhibition labels, observing exhibition)</i>	Recording Discussion <i>Participant discussed the exhibition content with/or asked questions to other visitors (family members, friends, or other museum visitors)</i>	Total
Participant 1 Interactive	... min ... sec			
Participant 1 Static	... min ... sec			
Participant 2 Interactive	... min ... sec			
Participant 2 Static	... min ... sec			
Participant 3 Interactive	... min ... sec			
Participant 3 Static	... min ... sec			
Participant 4 Interactive	... min ... sec			
Participant 4 Static	... min ... sec			
Participant 5 Interactive	... min ... sec			
Participant 5 Static	... min ... sec			
Participant 6 Interactive	... min ... sec			
Participant 6 Static	... min ... sec			
Participant 7 Interactive	... min ... sec			
Participant 7 Static	... min ... sec			
Participant 8 Interactive	... min ... sec			
Participant 8 Static	... min ... sec			
Participant 9 Interactive	... min ... sec			
Participant 9 Static	... min ... sec			
Participant 10 Interactive	... min ... sec			
Participant 10 Static	... min ... sec			

APPENDIX G : Pictures of researcher (Ng Yen Yen) collecting data.

Figure 6.7

Note: Prove of reseacher doing data collection across selected exhibits. Picture is taken on 17 April 2025. The paper reseacher holding is the observation form where reseacher record the number, interactions, and time spent of visitors viewing the selected exhibits.

Figure 6.8

Note: Prove of researcher doing data collection across selected exhibits. Picture is taken on 19 April 2025. The paper research holding is the observation form where researcher record the number, interactions, and time spent of visitors viewing the selected exhibits.

Figure 6.9

Note: Prove of researcher doing data collection across selected exhibits. Picture is taken on 20 April 2025. The paper research holding is the observation form where researcher record the number, interactions, and time spent of visitors viewing the selected exhibits.

Figure 7.0

Note: Researcher (right) and Annriza Teo (left), staff of Borneo Cultures Museum are taking a picture as a prove of completion of data collection.

APPENDIX H : Examples of Static Informational Exhibitions in Borneo Cultures Museum (BCM).

Figure 7.1

Temporary Static Informational Exhibit of Borneo Taxidermy Treasures

Note: The exhibit shows the static taxidermy of sea creatures with labels telling the history and the names of the exhibit's sea creatures.

Figure 7.2

Permanent Static Informational Exhibit of Borneo Cultures Museum

Note: Picture shows the Brunei Sultanate canons found in Samarahan. Labels are also provided to tell the history of the canons and Brunei Sultanate.

Figure 7.3

Note: Permanent static exhibits of Level 3, In Harmony with Nature.

Figure 7.4

Note: Permanent static exhibits of Level 3, In Harmony with Nature.

APPENDIX I : Examples of Interactive Visual Exhibitions in Borneo Cultures Museum (BCM).

Figure 7.5

Note: Figure above shows an exhibit that allows visitors to watch and listen to videos explaining the life and traditions of Borneo people in the past.

Figure 7.6

Note: Figure above shows an exhibit that mimics a Niah Cave. It has a screen that allows visitors to press and read the history of drawings in Niah Cave.

Figure 7.7

Note: Figure above shows an exhibit that shapes like a book and tells the history about Sarawak. The book can be flipped when visitors interact with it by waving their hand, which mimics the action of flipping a book.

Figure 7.8

Note: Figure above shows students looking at the interactive visual binoculars. When visitors look into the binoculars, they can see educational videos with caption about the life of locals.

APPENDIX J : Selected Exhibits

Figure 7.9

Note: Selected exhibit of Visual Interactive Exhibit (Puteri Santubong) from upper view.

Figure 8.0

Note: On the left, it is the selected exhibit of Static Informational Exhibit (Puteri Santubong) from upper view. On the right, the corner is where researcher stay to observe and record data.

APPENDIX K : Observation Records for Static Informational Exhibit (Kelidieng Burial Pole)

Date	17.04.25			
Exhibit	Static Informational Exhibit (Burial Pole Kelidieng)			
Observer name	Ng Yen Yen			
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 1	4 sec	X	6	280 s
Participant 2	12 sec	X		
Participant 3	53 sec	X		
Participant 4	26 sec	X		
Participant 5	30 sec	X		
Participant 6	57 sec	X		
Participant 7	18 sec	X		
Participant 8	8 sec	X		
Participant 9	6 sec	X		
Participant 10	21 sec	X		
Participant 11	9 sec	X		
Participant 12	17 sec	X		
Participant 13	8 sec	X		
Participant 14	15 sec	X		
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent				

Date	17.04.25			
Exhibit	Statis Informational exhibit (Bunai Polc'kelidierp)			
Observer name	Ng Yen Yen			
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 15	5 sec	X	2	274s
Participant 16	1 min 30 sec	X		
Participant 17	19 sec	X		
Participant 18	5 sec	✓		
Participant 19	8 sec	X		
Participant 20	27 sec	X		
Participant 21	9 sec	X		
Participant 22	36 sec	X		
Participant 23	14 sec	X		
Participant 24	17 sec	X		
Participant 25	20 sec	X		
Participant 26	24 sec	✓		
Participant				
Participant				
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent				

Date	19.04.25			
Exhibit	Bunai Pole "Kebudayaan"			
Observer name	Ng Yen Yen			
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 27	15 s	X	4	633 s
Participant 28	41 s	✓		
Participant 29	39 s	X		
Participant 30	50 s	X		
Participant 31	19 s	X		
Participant 32	3 m 15 s	X		
Participant 33	59 s	✓		
Participant 34	31 s	✓		
Participant 35	52 s	X		
Participant 36	18 s	X		
Participant 37	13 s	X		
Participant 38	35 s	✓		
Participant 39	23 s	X		
Participant 40	42 s	X		
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent				

Date	19.04.25			
Exhibit	Bunai pole "kelidierg"			
Observer name	Ng Yen Yen			
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 41	45 s	X	1	367 s
Participant 42	4 s	X		
Participant 43	18 s	X		
Participant 44	33 s	X		
Participant 45	59 s	X		
Participant 46	19 s	X		
Participant 47	11 s	X		
Participant 48	33 s	X		
Participant 49	12 s	X		
Participant 50	17 s	X		
Participant 51	42 s	✓		
Participant 52	24 s	X		
Participant 53	39 s	X		
Participant 54	11 s	X		
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent				

Date	19.04.25			
Exhibit	Bunjal Pole " Kelidierg "			
Observer name	Ng Yen Yen			
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 55	16 s	X	2	305s
Participant 56	24 s	X		
Participant 57	1 m	✓		
Participant 58	8 s	X		
Participant 59	4 s	X		
Participant 60	28 s	X		
Participant 61	29 s	✓		
Participant 62	3 s	X		
Participant 63	29 s	X		
Participant 64	29 s	X		
Participant 65	30 s	X		
Participant 66	15 s	X		
Participant 67	23 s	X		
Participant 68	12 s	X		
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent				

Date	20.04.25			
Exhibit	Burial site 'Kebiding'			
Observer name	Ng Yen Yen			
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 69	29s	X	6	453s
Participant 70	4s	✓		
Participant 71	44s	X		
Participant 72	17s	X		
Participant 73	40s	X		
Participant 74	1m 3s	✓		
Participant 75	19s	X		
Participant 76	37s	X		
Participant 77	12s	X		
Participant 78	15s	✓		
Participant 79	1m 3s	✓		
Participant 80	51s	✓		
Participant 81	14s	X		
Participant 82	45s	✓		
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent				

Date	20.04.25			
Exhibit	Buah Pale 'Kalideng'			
Observer name	Ng Yen Yen			
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 83	18 s	✓	3	104 s
Participant 84	34 s	✓		
Participant 85	41 s	✓		
Participant 86	11 s	✗		
Participant	53 s	✓		
Participant 7	24 s	✗		
Participant 8	20 s	✗		
Participant 9				
Participant 10				
Participant 11				
Participant 12				
Participant 13				
Participant 14				
Participant 15				
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent	$2405 \div 86 = 28.09s$ $= 28s$			

280
 274
 633
 367
 305
 453
 104

 2416 s

 0
 2
 4
 1
 2
 6
 3

APPENDIX L : Observation Records for Interactive Visual Exhibit (Puteri Santubong).

Date	17.04.25			
Exhibit	Visual Interactive Exhibit (Puteri Santubong)			
Observer name	Ng Yen Yen			
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 1	2 min 29 sec	✓	13	19205
Participant 2	2 min	✓		
Participant 3	2 min	✓		
Participant 4	1 min	✓		
Participant 5	3 min 27 sec	✓		
Participant 6	50 sec	X		
Participant 7	2 min 49 sec	✓		
Participant 8	2 min 24 sec	✓		
Participant 9	5 min 20 sec	✓		
Participant 10	2 min 37 sec	✓		
Participant 11	2 min	✓		
Participant 12	48 sec	✓		
Participant 13	1 min 8 sec	✓		
Participant 14	3 min 8 sec	✓		
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent				

Date	17.04.25			
Exhibit	Interactive Visual Exhibit (Puteri Santubong)			
Observer name	Ng Yen Yen			
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 15	1 min 31 sec	X	9	1686 s
Participant 16	7 min 8 sec	✓		
Participant 17	1 min	✓		
Participant 18	2 min 37 sec	✓		
Participant 19	34 sec	X		
Participant 20	7 sec	X		
Participant 21	29 sec	✓		
Participant 22	50 sec	✓		
Participant 23	2 min 49 sec	✓		
Participant 24	5 min 20 sec	✓		
Participant 25	3 min 08 sec	✓		
Participant 26	9 sec	X		
Participant 27	11 sec	X		
Participant 28	2 min 18 sec	✓		
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent				

Date	19.04.25			
Exhibit	Dufeni Sanyubong			
Observer name	Ng Yen Yen			
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 29	3 m 32 s	✓	13	2246 s
Participant 30	2 m 54 s	✓		
Participant 31	1 m 56 s	✓		
Participant 32	32 s	X		
Participant 33	2 m 20 s	✓		
Participant 34	2 m	✓		
Participant 35	4 m 50 s	✓		
Participant 36	2 m 0 s	✓		
Participant 37	3 m 5 s	✓		
Participant 38	3 m 41 s	✓		
Participant 39	1 m 32 s	✓		
Participant 40	2 m 32 s	✓		
Participant 41	4 m 3 s	✓		
Participant 42	2 m 21 s	✓		
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent				

4
60
240

Date	19. 04. 25			
Exhibit	Duyens' Santubong			
Observer name	Ng Yen Yen			
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 43	1 m 20 s	/	14	2064 s
Participant 44	1 m 7 s	/		
Participant 45	2 m 23 s	/		
Participant 46	2 m 59 s	/		
Participant 47	2 m 34 s	/		
Participant 48	3 m 10 s	/		
Participant 49	2 m 1 s	/		
Participant 50	3 m 9 s	/		
Participant 51	3 m 50 s	/		
Participant 52	3 m 14 s	/		
Participant 53	2 m 35 s	/		
Participant 54	1 m 09 s	/		
Participant 55	2 m 35 s	/		
Participant 56	2 m 18 s	/		
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent				

Date	20.04.25			
Exhibit	Pupeni San/ubong			
Observer name	Ny Yen Yen			
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 57	2 m 24 s	/	11	1917 s
Participant 58	3 m 29 s	/		
Participant 59	2 m 24 s	/		
Participant 60	40 s	X		
Participant 61	29 s	X		
Participant 62	1 m 32 s	/		
Participant 63	1 m 10 s	X		
Participant 64	4 m 3 s	/		
Participant 65	2 m 29 s	/		
Participant 66	2 m 28 s	/		
Participant 67	2 m 25 s	/		
Participant 68	3 m 50 s	/		
Participant 69	2 m 36 s	/		
Participant 70	1 m 58 s	/		
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent				

$$\begin{array}{r} 60 \\ 4 \\ \hline 240 \end{array}$$

Date				
Exhibit				
Observer name				
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 71	14 s	x		
Participant 72	5 m 21 s	/		
Participant 73	2 m 58 s	/		
Participant 74	2 m 16 s	/		
Participant 75	2 m 15 s	x		
Participant 76	2 m 28 s	x		
Participant 77	3 m 16 s	/		
Participant 78	3 m 19 s	/		
Participant 79	58 s	/		
Participant 80	1 m 42 s	/		
Participant 81	2 m 57 s	/		
Participant 82	4 m 4 s	/		
Participant 83	27 s	x		
Participant 84	2 m 12 s	/	10	2067 s
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent				

Date				
Exhibit				
Observer name				
Participant	Time period (Total time spent from starting to ending of checking out the exhibit)	Interaction (Participant interacted with the exhibition) Tick or Cross	Total interaction	Total time spent (sec)
Participant 85	4 m 33 s	/		
Participant 86	2 m 37 s	/		
Participant 87	50 s	x		
Participant 88	1 m 56 s	/		
Participant 89	2 m 30 s	/		
Participant 90	2 m 57 s	x		
Participant 8				
Participant 9				
Participant 10				
Participant 11				
Participant 12				
Participant 13				
Participant 14				
Participant 15			2	420 s
Formula	Total time spent / Total participant = Average time spent			
Average time spent	$12320 \div 86 = 143.26 s$ $= 2 m 23 s$			

1920
 1680
 2246
 2064
 1917
 2067
 420

 12320 s

 13
 9
 13
 14
 11
 10
 2

 72 interaf.

